

BIO-INSPIRED SOLAR-POWERED 3-D PRINTED BLENDED WING UAV

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ABSTRACT: This paper presents the design and development of a bio-inspired, solar-powered, 3D-printed blended wing unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) to improve aerodynamic efficiency, structural performance, and flight endurance. Inspired by bird flight, the UAV uses a blended wing body (BWB) design, integrating the wing and fuselage to minimize drag, optimize lift, and increase internal space for payloads. Fabricated with lightweight PLA via 3D printing, it allows precise production of complex geometries and rapid prototyping. Solar panels on the upper wing surface harness renewable energy, extending flight duration. Bio-inspired features, including tapered wings, smooth surface transitions, and optimized sweep angles, enhance aerodynamic stability, while carefully selected internal infill patterns balance strength and weight. Ground testing and controlled flight trials validate performance and durability. This work highlights the potential of combining bio-mimicry, additive manufacturing, and solar energy to create efficient, sustainable UAV platforms for surveillance, environmental monitoring, and aerial data collection.

KEYWORDS: Biomimicry, Solar-Powered UAV, Blended Wing Body, 3D Printing, Additive Manufacturing

1 INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are now indispensable instruments in aeronautical engineering, with a wide range of uses including disaster relief, environmental monitoring, and surveillance. These airborne platforms lower related expenses, improve operating safety, and offer improved data collecting capabilities. Innovative UAV designs that combine aerodynamic efficiency with sustainable energy sources are desperately needed, as demands for longer flight times and energy-efficient operation continue to rise.

The concept described here focuses on a UAV with a blended wing body (BWB) arrangement combined with a bio-inspired design. The BWB design unifies the fuselage and wings into a single, smooth surface, drawing inspiration from the aerodynamic prowess of birds. Sharp intersections that are present in traditional aircraft layouts are eliminated in this design, which lowers drag and increases structural efficiency. The BWB's larger interior capacity allows for the best possible configuration of payloads, batteries, and energy systems, improving maintainability and performance.

The limited endurance imposed by battery capacity is a significant obstacle in the UAV area. The UAV wing surfaces are equipped with solar photovoltaic (PV) technology to solve this problem, which enables the conversion of sunlight into electrical energy while in flight. By reducing reliance on fossil fuels, this innovation promises to increase operational flight times while simultaneously advancing green aviation. Even in situations with fluctuating illumination, a continuous power source is made possible by the incorporation of lightweight, flexible solar panels.

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA), an environmentally benign biodegradable polymer, is employed in Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM), one of the additive manufacturing techniques used in the manufacture. Rapid prototyping with accurate geometrical characteristics is made easier with this method, which also preserves the advantageous strength-to-weight ratio that is essential for flight efficiency. Customizable interior infill structures further guarantee the required stiffness with the least amount of weight loss. By combining sophisticated manufacturing, renewable energy harvesting, and bioinspired aerodynamics, this UAV prototype seeks to increase environmental sustainability and

durability. A system like this has potential for a variety of scientific and civilian tasks where long operational durations and flexible platforms are essential, such as academic research, agricultural monitoring, environmental surveillance, and disaster response.

2 OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of this study is to design and develop a solar-powered unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) using the additive manufacturing process (Fused Deposition Modelling). The work aims to fabricate a lightweight and efficient airframe optimized for solar integration. A solar power system consisting of photovoltaic panels, an MPPT controller, and a Li-Po battery is incorporated to enhance endurance. The performance of the UAV is evaluated through both theoretical analysis and experimental flight testing. The results are used to compare endurance and energy efficiency with and without solar assistance.

3 METHODOLOGY, DESIGN AND MATERIAL

3.1 Methodology

i)CAD Modelling: design process commenced with CAD modelling of the UAV using Autodesk Fusion 360, focusing on a blended wing body (BWB) configuration inspired by biomimicry principles. Key design parameters such as wingspan, taper ratio, aspect ratio, and sweep angles were optimized to balance aerodynamic efficiency, structural integrity, and internal volume utilization. The wing-body integration was designed to smooth transitions and reduce aerodynamic drag, while providing sufficient space for battery packs, electronics, and solar panel systems. Material selection prioritized Polylactic Acid (PLA), a biodegradable thermoplastic derived from renewable resources such as corn starch. PLA was chosen for its favourable strength-to-weight ratio, ease of printing, and environmental friendliness. It offers moderate tensile strength and stiffness suitable for UAV airframe components while enabling rapid prototyping through Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) 3D printing.

ii)Slicing and 3D Printing: fabrication was performed using an FDM 3D printer. The CAD designs were exported as STL files and processed via Prusa Slicer to generate G-code. Careful attention was given to print parameters including nozzle temperature, layer height, infill pattern, and wall thickness to optimize structural robustness while minimizing weight. Infill patterns such as gyroid or honeycomb were

utilized internally to provide strength and reduce material consumption. The print orientation and support structures were optimized to ensure dimensional accuracy and surface quality.

iii)Solar Power Integration: For the energy system, lightweight and flexible photovoltaic solar panels were integrated into the UAV's upper wing surfaces to maximize solar energy capture during flight. The solar power system was connected to a power management unit responsible for regulating energy flow between solar cells, lithium-polymer batteries, and the propulsion system. This configuration allows the UAV to utilize solar energy to supplement battery power, thereby extending flight endurance.

iv)Assembly and electronics configuration: Control surfaces consisted of elevons, combining elevator and aileron functions for pitch and roll control in the tailless BWB design. A brushless DC (BLDC) electric motor with optimal power-to-weight characteristics was selected to drive the propulsion system, paired with an electronic speed controller (ESC) for efficient throttle management.

v)Testing : Preliminary ground tests were conducted to assess print quality, part fitment, and balance. Subsequent flight testing was performed to evaluate the UAV's stability, control response, and endurance both without and with solar power integration. Data collection during flight utilized onboard sensors and manual observation to analyze performance metrics.

3.2 Preliminary Design

Table 1 . Design Parameters of UAV

Parameter	Symbol	Values
Wingspan	b	600 mm
Root Chord	C _r	200 mm
Tip Chord	C _t	31 mm
Taper Ratio	λ	0.103
Wing Area	S	49,650 mm ²
Aspect Ratio	AR	7.25
Mean Aerodynamic Chord	\hat{c}	122.5 mm
Quarter-Chord Sweep	$\Lambda_{c/4}$	56.3°
Wing MAC Location (\bar{x})	\bar{x}_{MAC}	78.5 mm from root LE
Fuselage Width	-	250 mm
Sweep Angle (Λ)	Λ	58°

The wingspan of the UAV is fixed at 600 mm, with a root chord of 200 mm and a tip chord of 31

mm, giving a taper ratio (λ) of 0.103—indicating a highly tapered wing profile. The total wing area, calculated using the trapezoidal wing area formula, is 49,650 mm² (0.04965 m²), and the aspect ratio (AR), which expresses the wing’s slenderness, is 7.25. These values suggest a wing optimized for aerodynamic performance with moderate lift and reduced induced drag. The Mean Aerodynamic Chord (MAC), which is the representative chord for aerodynamic force and moment calculations, is 122.5 mm, and its location (x_{MAC}) from the root leading edge is 78.5 mm—critical for centre of gravity and stability analysis. The wing features a quarter-chord sweep angle ($\Lambda_{c/4}$) of 56.3°, and a leading-edge sweep angle (Λ_{LE}) of 58°, both of which contribute to reduced drag and better high-speed characteristics, while also helping to maintain favourable aerodynamic centre positioning in a tailless configuration like a blended wing body (BWB). Additionally, the fuselage width is 250 mm, accommodating the integration of the central body with the wing planform.

Fig. 1. 2D drawing of BWB UAV

Fig. 2. 3D Top View of BWB UAV

3.3 Materials Used:

i) PLA (Polylactic Acid):

PLA is a biodegradable thermoplastic derived from renewable resources like corn starch and sugarcane, making it an eco-friendly choice for 3D printing applications. With a low density of 1.24 g/cm³, it is ideal for lightweight structures such as UAV components. PLA offers moderate

mechanical strength with a tensile strength of 50–70 MPa and an elastic modulus of 3.5 GPa, providing high stiffness but limited impact resistance. It melts at 180–220°C and prints best at 200–210°C, with minimal warping and no need for a heated bed. The material delivers a smooth, glossy surface finish, prints easily, and emits a sweet, non-toxic odor during fabrication, making it suitable for safe indoor use. While not ideal for high-load or flexible parts, PLA’s dimensional stability, biodegradability, and ease of printing make it excellent for non-structural UAV elements, prototypes, and academic projects.

Table. 2. Material Properties of PLA

Property	Typical Value	Remarks
Material Type	PLA	Bio-based, renewable (corn, sugarcane)
Density	1.24 g/cm ³	Light, lowload use
Melting Temp.	180–220°C	Print: 200–210°C
Tensile Strength	50–70 MPa	Good for light parts
Elastic Modulus	3.5 GPa	Stiff, brittle
Biodegradability	Yes	Eco-friendly, compostable
Surface Finish	Smooth, glossy	Good for aesthetics
Printability	Easy	Low warp, no heat bed (~60°C rec.)
Odor	Mild, sweet	Safe, non-toxic fumes

Fig. 3. Sliced part of UAV

4.1 Slicing of Part:

The 3D model of the UAV was processed using PrusaSlicer software to generate the toolpath required for fabrication. The slicing parameters were carefully selected to ensure dimensional accuracy, reduced printing time, and optimized strength-to-weight characteristics. A layer height of 0.2 mm was used to achieve a smooth surface finish while maintaining reasonable print duration. The honeycomb infill pattern with 20% infill density was chosen for its efficient internal structure, providing rigidity without adding excess weight. The model was oriented and sliced in sections to minimize support material usage and improve the bonding strength between layers. The resulting G-code file was then transferred to the FDM printer for fabrication using PLA filament.

4.2 Fabrication of Model:

Fig. 4. 3D Printing of UAV Parts

The UAV model was fabricated using a dual-nozzle FDM printer (Prusa i3 MK3S+ MMU2S). The 3D model was sliced in PrusaSlicer with a honeycomb infill pattern at 20% density and a layer height of 0.2 mm. Printing was performed with a nozzle temperature of 210 °C, a heated bed at 60 °C, and a print speed of 50 mm/s, ensuring proper adhesion and dimensional accuracy. The model was oriented to minimize support structures and optimize strength along critical load paths. The dual-nozzle setup allowed consistent deposition and reduced printing time for complex geometries, producing parts ready for post-processing and integration.

4.3 Assembly and System Integration:

Fig. 5. System Architecture of Assembly

After printing, the UAV components were carefully assembled, ensuring precise alignment and structural integrity. The solar panels, receiver, ESC, servos, BLDC motor, battery, and MPPT module were integrated into the airframe following the designed electrical and mechanical layout. Wiring was routed to minimize interference with moving parts and maintain the center of gravity. The solar panels were mounted on the wing surface to maximize exposure to sunlight, while the battery and MPPT module were positioned centrally to balance the aircraft. The assembled UAV was checked for proper control surface movement, secure motor mounting, and electrical connectivity, ensuring readiness for ground testing and subsequent flight experiments.

Fig. 6. Fully Assembled UAV

5. Result and Discussion

5.1 Total Weight Calculation:

The total weight of the UAV was estimated based on the combined mass of individual components. The airframe, fabricated using the FDM process, constitutes the major portion of the total weight at 450 g. The battery contributes 85 g, serving as the main power source, while the BLDC motor (72 g) and ESC (23 g) form the primary propulsion system. Control is achieved

through servo motors (18 g) and a receiver (15 g) for radio communication. The solar power system, consisting of solar panels (80 g) and an MPPT module (10 g), provides energy for solar-assisted endurance. The propeller adds an additional 14 g. The combined weight of all components results in a total UAV weight of approximately 794 g, which was maintained within the design limits to ensure stable flight and efficient power utilization.

Table. 3. Total weight calculation

Component	Total Weight (g)	Remarks
Airframe (Structure)	450 g	Intended total model weight
Battery	175 g	Main power source
Servo Motors	18 g	control surfaces
Receiver	15 g	Radio control
Motor	72 g	Main propulsion
ESC	23 g	Motor controller
Solar Panel	80 g	solar-assisted endurance
MPPT	10g	Solar module
Propeller	14g	Generate thrust
Total Weight	886 g	Final UAV Weight

5.2 Theoretical Calculation:

- Mass, $m = 0.886 \text{ kg}$
- Gravity, $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$
- Weight, $W = m \cdot g = 8.69166 \text{ N}$
- Battery energy (full), $E_{\text{full}} = 24.42 \text{ Wh}$
- Usable energy (80%), $E_{\text{usable}} = 19.54 \text{ Wh}$
- Propulsive efficiency, $\eta = 0.6$
- Solar power assumed, $P_{\text{solar}} = 9.60 \text{ W}$ (6x4V panels)

i)Thrust required:

Thrust (T): $T = R \cdot W$

For $R = 0.8 \rightarrow T = 0.8 \times 8.69166 = 6.953 \text{ N}$

For $R = 1.0 \rightarrow T = 1.0 \times 8.69166 = 8.692 \text{ N}$

iii)Electrical Power (P_{elec}):

$P_{\text{elec}} = P_{\text{prop}} / \eta$

For $R = 0.8 \rightarrow P_{\text{elec}} = 92.71 \text{ W}$

For $R = 1.0 \rightarrow P_{\text{elec}} = 144.86 \text{ W}$

Performance Calculations Without Solar Assistance

ii) Propulsive Power (P_{prop}):

$P_{\text{prop}} = T \cdot V$

For $R = 0.8 \rightarrow P_{\text{prop}} = 6.953 \times 8 = 55.63 \text{ W}$

For $R = 1.0 \rightarrow P_{\text{prop}} = 8.692 \times 10 = 86.92 \text{ W}$

iv)Endurance :

$t = E_{\text{usable}} / P_{\text{elec}}$

For $R = 0.8 \rightarrow t = 12.64 \text{ min}$

For $R = 1.0 \rightarrow t = 8.09 \text{ min}$

Fig. 7. Graphical representation of Endurance Vs Thrust to Weight Ratio

v)Range:

$\text{Range} = V \cdot t \cdot 3.6$

For $R = 0.8 \rightarrow \text{Range} = 6.07 \text{ km}$

For $R = 1.0 \rightarrow \text{Range} = 4.86 \text{ km}$

Fig. 8. Graphical representation of Range Vs Thrust to Weight Ratio

Performance Calculations With Solar Assistance

i)Net Power (P_{net}):

$P_{\text{net}} = P_{\text{elec}} - P_{\text{solar}}$

For $R = 0.8 \rightarrow P_{\text{net}} = 83.11 \text{ W}$

For $R = 1.0 \rightarrow P_{\text{net}} = 135.26 \text{ W}$

$t = E_{\text{usable}} / P_{\text{net}}$

For $R = 0.8 \rightarrow t = 14.10 \text{ min}$

For $R = 1.0 \rightarrow t = 8.67 \text{ min}$

Fig. 9. Graphical representation of Endurance Vs Thrust to Weight Ratio with Solar Assistance

iii)Range:

Range = $V \cdot t \cdot 3.6$
 For $R = 0.8 \rightarrow$ Range = 6.77 km
 For $R = 1.0 \rightarrow$ Range = 5.20 km

Fig. 10. Graphical representation of Range Vs Thrust to Weight Ratio

5.3 Theoretical Conclusion

The theoretical calculations gives that With solar assistance, the UAV’s performance shows a measurable improvement compared to batteryonly operation. For a thrust-to-weight ratio (R) of

0.8, the endurance increases from 12.64 min to 14.10 min, an improvement of 11.5%, while the range increases from 6.07 km to 6.77 km, a rise of 11.5%. Similarly, for $R = 1.0$, endurance improves from 8.09 min to 8.67 min, an increase of 7.2%, and range improves from 4.86 km to 5.20 km, an increase of 7.0%. Hence, solar power integration provides a significant performance enhancement, especially at lower thrust conditions.

5.4 Experimental Validation

i)without solar(on ground):

In the ground-based experimental tests conducted without actual flight, the endurance of the UAV system was measured for different thrust-toweight ratios. For $R = 0.8$, the observed endurance was 8 minutes, while for $R = 1.0$, the endurance reduced to 6 minutes due to the higher power demand at greater thrust levels. These experimental results are consistent with theoretical predictions, However, the measured values are slightly lower than theoretical estimates, primarily due to real-world factors such as motor efficiency losses, propeller slip, aerodynamic drag from static testing conditions, and internal resistance of the battery.

Fig. 11. Graphical representation of Endurance Vs Thrust to Weight Ratio without Solar(Exp)

i)with solar(on ground):

In the solar-assisted configuration, the endurance of the UAV system showed an improvement across the tested thrust-to-weight ratios. For $R = 0.8$, the measured endurance increased to 9 minutes, while for $R = 1.0$, the endurance was observed to be 6.5 minutes. This demonstrates the beneficial impact of solar energy in supplementing battery power, especially under lower thrust conditions where power demand is relatively lower. The trend of decreasing endurance with increasing thrust-to-weight ratio remains consistent, but the solar input provides a measurable extension of flight time. As with the nonsolar tests, the endurance values are slightly below theoretical predictions due to practical inefficiencies such as partial solar panel coverage, conversion losses, and non-ideal incident light conditions during testing.

Fig. 11. Graphical representation of Endurance Vs Thrust to Weight Ratio with Solar(Exp)

6. Conclusion:

The study successfully demonstrated the design, development, and performance evaluation of a bioinspired, solar-assisted blended wing UAV fabricated using 3D printing technology. Theoretical and experimental analyses confirmed that integrating solar energy significantly enhances the endurance and range of the UAV compared to conventional battery-only operation.

Theoretical results indicated an endurance improvement of 11.5% at a thrust-to-weight ratio $R = 0.8$ and 7.2% at $R = 1.0$, with corresponding range increases of 11.5% and 7.0%, respectively. Experimental ground tests further validated these findings, showing an endurance rise from 8 minutes to 9 minutes at $R = 0.8$, and from 6 minutes to 6.5 minutes at $R = 1.0$ under solar-assisted conditions. Although the measured values were slightly below theoretical predictions due to real-world inefficiencies such as solar conversion losses, propeller slip, and motor inefficiencies, the overall trend consistently confirmed the positive impact of solar integration. The UAV exhibited improved power sustainability, particularly under lower thrust conditions, highlighting the potential of solar-assisted hybrid power systems in extending flight duration.

In conclusion, the integration of solar energy into lightweight 3D-printed UAVs offers a promising pathway for enhanced endurance, reduced dependence on battery capacity, and improved operational efficiency, paving the way for future developments in sustainable unmanned aerial systems.

Future Scope:

Future work can focus on conducting in-flight endurance testing under varying solar irradiance conditions to better evaluate real-time performance. Optimization of solar panel efficiency, power management circuitry, and aerodynamic integration can further enhance energy utilization. The use of lightweight composite materials and high-capacity lithium-polymer or solid-state batteries may also improve payload capability and flight duration. Additionally, implementing maximum power point tracking (MPPT) systems and autonomous energy management algorithms can enable more efficient hybrid power operation. Extending this research to larger-scale UAVs and continuous flight missions could significantly advance sustainable aerial surveillance and remote sensing applications.

Reference:

1. Hassanalian, M., Abdelkefi, A.: Classifications, applications, and design challenges of drones: A review. *Progress in Aerospace Sciences* 91, 99–131 (2017).
2. Noth, A., Siegart, R., Engel, W.: Design of solar powered airplanes for continuous flight. Autonomous Systems Lab, ETH Zurich, Switzerland (2008).
3. Zhang, X., Ma, Q., Zhang, H., Zhang, C.: Design and analysis of a solar-powered unmanned aerial vehicle with a blended wing body configuration. *Aerospace Science and Technology* 98, 105667 (2020).
4. Pires, B., Melo, F.: Development of 3D printed UAV structures: Design, fabrication, and testing. *Additive Manufacturing* 28, 605–620 (2019).
5. Roskam, J.: *Airplane Design Part VI: Preliminary Calculation of Aerodynamic, Thrust and Power Characteristics*. DARcorporation, Kansas (2003).
6. Green, M.A., Dunlop, E.D., Hohl-Ebinger, J., Yoshita, M., Kopidakis, N., Hao, X.: Solar cell efficiency tables (Version 65). *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications* 32(4), 426–438 (2024).